

YOUTH ENTREPRENEURSHIP AND COMMUNITY TOURISM IN INDIA

– A CONCEPTUAL STUDY

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ABSTRACT

The tourism industry has long been a source of economic growth and job creation, and with a growing young population, youth entrepreneurship in this sector has the potential to drive even for greater development. In India, where both tourism and youth entrepreneurship are thriving, there is a unique opportunity to connect the two and create a more sustainable future. However, there are still significant challenges that must be addressed in order to fully realize the potential of youth entrepreneurship in the tourism business. Limited access to resources, inadequate infrastructure, and a lack of awareness about opportunities in the industry are just a few of the barriers that must be overcome. Despite these challenges, there are many initiatives already underway that are empowering young people and promoting sustainable tourism practices. Community-based tourism projects are providing young entrepreneurs with adequate resources and support which they need to start and grow their businesses. By working with local communities, these initiatives can also promote cultural preservation and responsible tourism practices, further benefiting both local entrepreneurs and tourists alike. This paper tries to bring out the relation between youth entrepreneurship and community based tourism.

Key words: Tourism, Community Tourism, Youth Entrepreneurship, Sustainable Tourism

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INTRODUCTION

Youth is the future of every nation & inheritors of the earth tomorrow. When a country has a healthy youth population, you will find the country making headway in terms of overall development and progress. One of the major challenges faced by most of the countries in the world today is to do with Youth unemployment. The overall unemployment rate is growing at an alarming speed. Amongst the unemployed, the unemployment of youth seems to be alarming. Entrepreneurship in any society is a sign of progress. Youth entrepreneurship has an impact on social as well as cultural and economic progress of the society. Building an environment that promotes creatively and provides opportunities for entrepreneurship calls for multi pronged strategies implementation and involvement at all levels including Government, industry, political, social as well as educational sectors. According to statistics, 54% of our population is under the age of 35 and close to 15 million enter the workforce every year. The only way through which enough jobs can be created for such a huge populous, consistently, is by creating an environment for entrepreneurship and innovation. The young innovative minds that we see around us; and government and industry initiatives which are there to promote innovation and entrepreneurship, India will soon be much up in the global entrepreneurship rankings.

India has become an emerging market for global investors and entrepreneurship is majorly contributing to the country's economy. A stable business environment, market-oriented reforms and key initiatives like Make in India, Digital India, Mudra Yojana, Atal Innovation Mission, 59 minute loan, Stand up India and Start-Up India are encouraging aspiring and ambitious young Indians. Also, with the number of incubators increasing by 40% every year, startups are staring at a bright future.

These flagship programmes are addressing various elements of entrepreneurship ecosystem including organising grand challenges, funding support, creation of new incubators and capacity building of existing incubators, ease of doing business, tax benefits. Apart from the high technology and advanced innovation based entrepreneurship, Government is equally supportive of large scale entrepreneurship based on continuous/incremental innovation or existing knows how. This entrepreneurial ecosystem has the largest potential to create employment across sectors and geographies for all socio-economic categories of our youth. Within this ecosystem, Government is equally committed to support women and SC/ST Communities, people from Difficult Areas and Divyang Jan for entrepreneurship promotion.

Ministry of Skill Development and Entrepreneurship plays an important role to promote this large scale entrepreneurial ecosystem, together with the Skill development initiatives for entrepreneurship. Ministry has undertaken consistent and strategically planned efforts to promote entrepreneurship and provide necessary support to skilled candidates interested in starting their enterprise. As a first step, Common Norms for Skill Development 2015 recognizes self employment at par with placement as outcome benchmark of skill trainings. Additionally, a 20 hr mandatory module on entrepreneurial training has been included in short term skill training programme. Further, Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Kendras have been converted to Entrepreneurship Hubs to facilitate entrepreneurship in the district by providing interested trainees mentoring and handholding support.

Ministry has also collaborated with Department of Financial Services, SIDBI, Rural Self Employment Training Institutes (RSETIs) and Civil Society organizations like DeAsra to impart the knowledge base on enterprise start-up, mentorship and handholding and to facilitate credit linkages. Towards creating the favorable environment for entrepreneurship, Ministry has instituted National Entrepreneurship Awards to recognize and honor outstanding young first generation entrepreneurs and organizations/individuals committed for entrepreneurship development. The Awards has been expanded to make the scheme more inclusive by honoring entrepreneurs from varied socio-economic backgrounds across sectors from all the geographies of the country.

New innovators and potential entrepreneurs are helping their businesses in the Indian market daily. The current Indian entrepreneurship world is becoming a highly favorable market for any company to invest in. Also, most Indian companies have marked their potential in international trade and shown the growth of entrepreneurship in India.

OBJECTIVES OF THE RESEARCH

The objective of the research is to understand the significance of Youth entrepreneurship and Community Based Tourism. The study further highlights the scope and importance of various measures taken to boost youth entrepreneurship in India and the development of Community based tourism. Through the study it helps to correlate scope of youth entrepreneurship and community based tourism.

METHODOLOGY

The research design is exploratory in nature as it aims to explore the concept of youth entrepreneurship and community tourism in India. It will include a review of existing literature and case studies in the field. It provides insights into the concept of youth entrepreneurship and community tourism in India. The findings of the study will contribute to the development of strategies that can promote youth entrepreneurship and community tourism in India.

Figure 1 The influencing factors associated with youth entrepreneurship and community-based tourism

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

(Diman and Dubay , 2011) have investigated various sustainable tourism development dimensions in which the conclusion indicates that there is major differences in stake holders in terms of perception of different aspects of tourism development. As per the study of (Barkaukiene and snieska, 2013) any kind of tourism which protects and promotes environment, natural and other resources will pave way for sustainable tourism. Community based tourism focuses on the host community where the local community involve in planning and developing which in order will create a more sustainable industry (Hall, 1996). It takes the social, cultural and environmental aspects into account, where the entire process is owned and managed by the

community, where in the visitors will get an awareness on the local culture and local ways of life (REST Project 1997 and REST 2003). The indigenous people and the people of the local community is involved in Community based tourism which will help in their all round development (Mann 2001). Tourism entrepreneurship is a process which focuses towards the tourism resources to be used in line with the tourists demands (Aslan, 2019). Tourism entrepreneurship is important for the success of hospitality and tourism industry and makes a significance contribution to the country's economy (Booth, P., Chaperon, S. A., Kennell, J. S., & Morrison, A. M. 2020) Playing an important role in social capital, tourism sector as a very close relationship with social entrepreneurship which blends social benefits and motives for profit (Dias, Á., & Silva, G. M. 2021) Small scale tourism entrepreneurship should be given more priority as the tourism destinations have more potential for entrepreneurs (Medina, S. A. J., Arteaga-Ortiz, J., Naumchik, R. M., & Pellejero, M. 2020). The present study analyses the scope for youth entrepreneurship in community tourism in India

RESEARCH FINDINGS

YOUTH ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN INDIA – AN OVERVIEW

India is a land of diverse cultures, languages, and traditions. It is also a country of immense entrepreneurial opportunities. With a booming population of youth, India has become a hub of startup businesses, where young entrepreneurs are driving change and innovation.

One of the key sectors where youth entrepreneurship is thriving is in community tourism. Community tourism involves local communities taking control of their own tourism industry, with the aim of improving their economic and social well-being. This has become an increasingly popular model in India, where there are many rural areas with untapped tourism potential.

The idea behind community tourism is to create a more sustainable tourism model, where tourists get to experience authentic local cultures, while the local communities benefit economically. This can help to create a more equitable distribution of wealth, and reduce the negative impacts of mass tourism.

One of the most successful examples of community tourism in India is the village of Kutch in Gujarat. Kutch is a rural area with a rich cultural heritage, but it had been largely ignored by mainstream tourism. A group of young entrepreneurs decided to change this by

setting up a community tourism project, which involved training local people to offer homestays, food experiences, and cultural tours to tourists.

The project was a huge success, and today Kutch is a popular destination for travelers who want to experience rural India. The local communities have benefited greatly, with many families earning extra income from tourism-related activities. This has helped to create more sustainable livelihoods, and has also helped to preserve the local culture and traditions.

Another example of youth entrepreneurship in community tourism is the city of Jaipur in Rajasthan. Jaipur is a popular tourist destination, but there are many neighborhoods in the city that have been left out of the tourism boom. A group of young entrepreneurs decided to address this by setting up a walking tour that took tourists through some of the city's lesser-known neighborhoods.

The walking tour was a hit with tourists, who appreciated the chance to experience the real Jaipur. The local communities also benefited, as the walking tour brought in much-needed income, and helped to preserve the local heritage.

These examples demonstrate how youth entrepreneurship can drive change in the tourism industry, and create more sustainable tourism models. By empowering local communities, young entrepreneurs can help to create a more equitable distribution of wealth, and promote cultural preservation.

However, youth entrepreneurship in community tourism is not without its challenges. Many rural areas lack the infrastructure and resources necessary to develop a successful tourism industry. There is also a need for more government support and investment in rural tourism projects.

Despite these challenges, youth entrepreneurship in community tourism has the potential to transform the tourism industry in India. By empowering local communities and promoting sustainable tourism models, young entrepreneurs can help to create a more inclusive and equitable society.

NEED OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP FOR ECONOMIC GROWTH

Entrepreneurship is an instrument of social change and economic development. Entrepreneurs firmly believe that it is entrepreneurship that will beat and transform the market with new-age technologies.

The following factors determine why entrepreneurship is needed in economic development.

1. Innovation

Innovation is the primary element of entrepreneurship. New-age entrepreneurs are passionate about innovations in technology and business models. Some of the primary examples of this are Airbnb, Innova8, Ola, Zinerr etc. These companies not only bring innovation in technology but also created unique business models that never existed before.. Policymakers of an economy consider innovation while creating a road map for the country's economic development. Innovation creates market ease and new opportunities and encourages consumption. Entrepreneurship in India is important as it inspires innovation

2. Employment

Employment is an important factor in the development of any economy. A low employment rate indicates the poor health of an economy. An economy needs to generate more jobs and wage opportunities to accelerate growth. It plays an important role in job creation. The bigger the enterprise, the more job and salary opportunities are created. Hence, the need for entrepreneurship in India becomes important for economic development.

3. Living standard

The standard of living is, in a way, directly proportional to employment. Because employment pays people, they spend their money on the purchase of goods and services. Therefore, the consumption rate increases in an economy, and so does the production rate. This eventually raises the basic wage, and people are able to consume higher quality goods and services.

4. Social change

Social entrepreneurship is a modern term that encourages entrepreneurs to bring about change in society. For example, crowd funding companies are usually involved in social work such as raising funds for NGOs. Their businesses bring positive changes to society. They not only help the needy but also spread social awareness. A prosperous society facilitates the path of community development. Therefore, the need for entrepreneurship in India is important as it brings together social reform and economic development.

5. Research and Development

Research and development are the progress of innovation. When an entrepreneur comes up with innovative ideas and builds a business from them, they need to continuously develop

their innovation to keep up with the market and improve the user experience. As the enterprise grows, they spend more resources on research and development, which leads to technological progress.

Technological advancement not only supports a particular company but the entire nation. It contributes to the growth of science and technology. The economy further utilizes these developments to implement in various sectors to make progress.

CHANGING FACE OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN INDIA

Entrepreneurship in India was on a rough path. Moreover, after independence, it had a terrible impact. However, with policies and hard work our country was able to overcome it at one point in time. Now with an innovative mind, India is gaining dominance in the market. And entrepreneurship opportunities will increase in India. For policymakers and business owners, it is essential to consider the relationship between entrepreneurship and economic development. Knowing the pros and cons of entrepreneurship makes it possible to adopt a balanced approach. An approach to developing the importance of entrepreneurship, which can have positive economic and social impact. Conclusively, we can look at various practical, direct and indirect factors that come into effect due to entrepreneurship. And why entrepreneurship is essential to an economy. We should not underestimate the impact of entrepreneurship on the economy. Entrepreneurship in India leaves a positive impact on the economy.

COMMUNITY BASED TOURISM

Community-based entrepreneurship is the process of recognizing, creating (i.e. developing, collectivizing and evaluating), and exploiting opportunities to collectively create future goods and services that provide economic, social and/or ecological benefits for the local communities in which they are embedded, and/or society at large. Community Based Tourism is a tool that strengthens the ability of tourism communities to manage resources while ensuring local community participation. This tourism can help the local community in Generating income, Diversifying local economy, Preserving culture, Conserving environment, Providing educational opportunities.

BENEFITS OF COMMUNITY BASED ENTREPRENEURSHIP

Community based Entrepreneurship brings in lots of benefits to the local community and enriches their standards of living. Some of the major benefits include:

- Creation of income, economic development and poverty alleviation.
- Improved local services (as compensation for gaps in governmental support)
- Conservation of local culture and alignment of local culture with market requirements
- Environmental benefits-reduced emissions & promotion of environmentally superior modes of production and consumption
- Social inclusion and empowerment of certain groups like indigenous people, farmers, women, disabled people, Improved social cohesion, Increase in social wealth creation and local resilience Encouragement of and inspiration for individual entrepreneurship
- Sustainable use of natural resources.

CHALLENGES OF COMMUNITY BASED TOURISM

Although locally driven community-based tourism (CBT) approaches have helped the underprivileged community in many regions with high unemployment (Marsh, 2022), it is also found that CBT enterprises and initiatives have not always been able to see the expected results, and therefore, many of them are unable to claim success (Muckosy & Mitchell, 2008; Goodwin & Santilli 2009). Some of the common challenges of successful implementation and promotion of Community Based Tourism (CBT) are:

- Lack of awareness and understanding of the benefits of CBT
- Lack of marketing and promotion
- Lack of government support and funding
- Lack of security and pro-poor management
- Conflict in leadership
- Lack of monitoring and planning
- Limited scope for income generation
- Gap between the academic definitions and the way it is implemented by the practitioners

YOUTH ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN COMMUNITY BASED TOURISM

Youth entrepreneurship and community-based tourism are two concepts that can be effectively blended to create innovative and sustainable tourism models. Community-based

tourism involves the active participation of local communities in the development and management of tourism activities. This approach has proven to be effective in promoting sustainable tourism practices and supporting local economic development. Youth entrepreneurship, on the other hand, refers to the active involvement of young people in the creation and management of businesses. Youth entrepreneurs bring fresh ideas, innovation, and energy to the business world, and can play a significant role in the development of community-based tourism initiatives.

Blending youth entrepreneurship and community-based tourism can bring about several benefits. Firstly, it can help to create new job opportunities for young people in rural areas, thereby contributing to the economic development of these communities. By providing young people with the opportunity to start their own businesses, it can also promote youth empowerment and create a sense of ownership among local communities. Secondly, youth entrepreneurship can help to drive innovation and creativity in community-based tourism initiatives. Young entrepreneurs are often more open to new ideas and trends, and can bring a fresh perspective to traditional tourism activities. By working together with local communities, youth entrepreneurs can help to create unique and authentic tourism experiences that attract a diverse range of travelers. Thirdly, blending youth entrepreneurship and community-based tourism can help to promote sustainable tourism practices. Young entrepreneurs are often more aware of the importance of environmental sustainability and social responsibility. By incorporating these values into their businesses, they can help to promote sustainable tourism practices and contribute to the conservation of natural and cultural resources.

By promoting youth empowerment, driving innovation, and promoting sustainable tourism practices, this approach can help to create more inclusive, equitable, and sustainable tourism models in India. It is therefore important to continue to invest in youth entrepreneurship and community-based tourism initiatives, and to create an enabling environment that supports the development of these initiatives.

CONCLUSION

Youth entrepreneurship in community tourism has the potential to transform the tourism industry in India. By empowering local communities and promoting sustainable tourism models, young entrepreneurs can help to create a more equitable and inclusive society. The success

stories of Kutch and Jaipur demonstrate that with the right support and resources, rural areas can develop thriving tourism industries that benefit both tourists and locals alike. However, there are still challenges to be addressed, such as the lack of infrastructure and government support. It is therefore important to continue to invest in youth entrepreneurship and community tourism, in order to create more sustainable and inclusive tourism models in India.

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